

Report on the first Focus Group

REPORT ON THE FOCUS GROUP ON THE THEME: "SOFT SKILLS OF YOUTH NEEDED FOR ENGAGEMENT IN THE WORK SPHERE AND LAUNCHING ENTREPRENEURIAL BUSINESS"

In the focus group on the theme: **"Soft Skills of Youth Needed for Engagement in the Work Sphere and Launching Entrepreneurial Business"** 22 participants took part. Their characteristics are as follows:

1. Expertise Structure:

- Nine participants are experts in the field of **Human Resources (HR)**.
- Nine participants come from the field of **entrepreneurship**.
- Four participants hold managerial or other positions within their companies.

2. Positions:

○ **HR Participants:**

- Three work in a bank and currently hold the position of **Branch Manager**.
- Two work in a marketing company and communication.
- One works in a company dealing with software development and currently holds the position of **Human Resource Manager**.
- Another HR participant works in the fashion sector, hotel industry, and distribution and logistics service company.

3. Entrepreneurship Participants:

- One holds the position of **Chief Operating Officer**.
- Another is the **Chief Financial Officer**.
- One is the **Chief Executive Officer**.
- One participant from the field of entrepreneurship currently holds the position of **software developer**.
- Two participants hold the position of **General Director/Manager – Owner** in the IT sector.
- One participant is the founder and **General Manager** at a research and consulting service company.
- Two participants hold the position of **Co-Founder and General Manager** in a consulting service company.

4. Private Company Participant:

- One participant from the field of private companies holds the position of **manager** in fields related to furniture production, insurance, beauty centers, and banking.

5. Gender:

- Twelve participants are **male**, while ten participants are **female**.

I The first group of questions were aimed to determine the attitudes of the respondents about the necessary interpersonal and intrapersonal skills that are important for young people for successful integration into the world of work and running an entrepreneurial business.

In response to the question about the importance of *communication skills*, eighteen out of twenty-two respondents stated that they **are extremely important**. One of the respondents from the field of **entrepreneurship** emphasized that communication skills **are very important at the beginning** of an entrepreneurial business in order to obtain the necessary information important for this phase of the entrepreneurial process. Another respondent, also from the field of entrepreneurship, emphasized that when it comes to communication skills, **active listening is very important**. In this regard, he emphasized that in business he respects the “20:80” rule and stated: “I am here to talk very little and to hear a lot”. The same respondent stated that communication skills are important for gaining trust with clients.

In response to the question about the importance of *social skills* in the business sphere, respondents expressed different attitudes. However, the majority belong to the group of those who believe that **these skills are important**. One of the respondents, a manager, emphasized that people are the quality that makes a company, and that the character of employees is crucial in relation to knowledge and communication, which he believes can be learned later. The respondent from the **field of HR** pointed out that when choosing employees, it is of crucial importance to choose people who can function with others, to fit into the work environment, to ask for help if they need it, but also to provide it to others as needed.

In response to the question about the importance of *emotional intelligence*, the respondents stated that it **is very important**. However, it was pointed out that **this skill needs to be worked on**, i.e., developed through various trainings, as it is not innate. A respondent from the HR field emphasized that this skill is especially **important for managers**.

When it comes to *personal integrity*, the respondents’ answers regarding the importance of this trait are different, but the majority of the participants stand out that this trait is **important** in business. One of the respondents from the field of entrepreneurship emphasized that although emotional intelligence is an individual characteristic and to some extent innate, this skill is still built throughout the development of the individual and emphasized that “too much emotionality is harmful, too little emotionality can lead to great losses and therefore an optimal level of emotional intelligence is required in business”.

Finally, when it comes to the importance of *persistence and perseverance in achieving career goals*, 18 respondents believe that these traits are **important**, and some even very important. One of the respondents from the field of entrepreneurship emphasized that “self-confidence is built through small victories”, and another respondent from the field of entrepreneurship followed up on the same conclusion, adding that “especially for entrepreneurs, in order to be persistent and persistent, it is of great importance to set realistic goals.” A respondent from the **HR field** emphasized that **persistence is a very important** trait if you want to do your job well. “It can’t bother, but it shouldn’t turn into stubbornness.” The respondent from the field of management emphasized that *persistence* is a very important trait and that an individual should live his job in order to do it successfully but also enjoy his job and not come to work with negative premises. Some of the interesting findings were also:

- **Young people** often enter the business world with a primary motivation: **money**.
- Personal **psychological tests** have proven valuable for evaluating candidates and fostering self-improvement.

In **summary**, when examining the attitudes of respondents about the **necessary interpersonal and intrapersonal skills that are important for young people to successfully integrate into the world of work and run an entrepreneurial business**, it was found that effective **communication and social skills** are vital for **team dynamics, conflict resolution, and building customer relationships**. Furthermore, the respondents state that **personal integrity and persistence** are integral for professional **growth and achieving career** goals. Finally, they assert that **emotional intelligence** and **setting realistic objectives** contribute to long-term success in business.

II The second group of questions related to examining the **attitudes of respondents regarding whether and which managerial skills and problem-solving skills are important for successfully starting and running a business**.

In response to the question of how important **planning and organizing skills** are for successfully starting a business and success at work, twenty one out of twenty-two respondents answered that these skills are **very important**. An **HR representative** highlighted the significance of having **clear goals and plans**. Without proper planning, it becomes challenging to assess progress and determine which phase of a project or business endeavor we are in. Interestingly, a representative from **entrepreneurship acknowledged the difficulty of planning specific steps** in entrepreneurial ventures but underscored the importance of having overarching goals.

In response to the question about the importance of **time management skills** for efficient goal realization, the respondents agreed that this skill is **very important**. A respondent from the field of **entrepreneurship** highlighted that this skill is **insufficiently developed** in people. According to him, young individuals need to make conscious decisions about how to allocate their free time. They can choose between developing business ideas or other activities.

Regarding the importance of some managerial skills, respondents who work in the field of human resources put specific emphasis on **managerial skills for creating work teams** that will be led by leaders. The leaders portrayed them as persons who will encourage good team spirit, proper distribution of responsibility, creating an environment with open communication and sharing of ideas/solutions, will encourage others, as well as persons who know how to receive and give feedback.

One of the interviewees also emphasized that "**resilience** is a key managerial ability, i.e. to have the ability to assess and determine the correct way to convey or not success, failure, stress, etc."

When it comes to **problem-solving skills** for successful goal realization, the respondents held varying opinions. These opinions ranged from which management level should be decisive in solving problems to the level of significance attributed to this skill. The respondent from the HR field highlighted several crucial managerial skills: *flexibility* (the ability to adapt to changing circumstances, readiness *for changes* (being prepared to handle shifts and adjustments), and *openness to communication at all levels* (encouraging effective communication throughout the organization).

The respondent from the field the entrepreneurship singled out specific qualities such as: *delegation* (skill of entrusting tasks to others effectively), *constant development* (commitment to ongoing learning and growth) and *focus* (the ability to discern and prioritize important aspects of work).

The second group of questions focused on respondents' attitudes regarding the **importance of adapting to market changes**. Most respondents believe that this skill is **important**. A representative from the field of entrepreneurship highlighted that their entrepreneurial company **made major changes in operations over three years** to adapt to the market. Other representatives from the field of entrepreneurship also **emphasized the importance of adapting to the market**.

In summary, when **examining the attitudes of respondents** regarding whether and which managerial skills and problem-solving skills are important for successfully starting and running a business, the respondents state that **planning and time management skills play critical roles** in achieving success, whether in business ventures or professional endeavors. However, the respondents believe that **time management skills should be more developed than they currently are**. Furthermore, the respondents emphasize that **problem-solving skills are essential for successful goal realization**, and different perspectives highlight various aspects of these skills. They also assert that **adaptability, effective communication, delegation, continuous learning, and focus contribute to effective problem-solving in different contexts**. Finally, they recognize the **significance of adapting to market shifts** in order to achieve business success. Entrepreneurs, in particular, understand the need for **flexibility and proactive adjustments** to stay competitive in a dynamic marketplace.

III The third group of questions related to examining **the attitudes of respondents about whether information, opportunity, and risk management skills are important for successful integration into the world of work and starting a business**.

In response to the question about the importance of **critical thinking skills** for recognizing market opportunities, the respondents had different answers, with 16 respondents considering this skill important. They also state that It is important to have a control of information and to be able to summarize it simply, to be able to look for opportunities and to know how to manage risks, both when starting a business and in everyday work.

A representative from the field of **entrepreneurship** pointed out that information from the environment **is important**, but that he was also **guided by a feeling**, i.e., intuition in his business. In addition, he pointed out that it is necessary to invest both effort and time for opportunities to open up themselves. He also stated that one should be informed and use all the possible channels to make a final decision.

The importance of possessing **the ability to cope with uncertainty and risk for integration into economic flows (starting a business) and successful management** was also a topic of discussion. The respondents held different views on this issue, which can be attributed to the different fields they belong to. Some respondents from the field of **entrepreneurship** believe that **young people can accept higher risks** because they don't have much to lose. Respondents from the **HR field** emphasize that company management must create a **culture of critical and analytical thinking**. They advocate for establishing a **system to measure key performance indicators (KPIs)**. One HR respondent pointed out that risk should be reduced to a minimum, even if it significantly limits work. **Entrepreneurs with more experience** believe that collecting **as much information as possible is crucial** for risk reduction. They focus on developing and utilizing skills to approach emerging risks willingly and skillfully. The general attitude of respondents from the **field of**

entrepreneurship is that **risk should be minimized, but not entirely avoided**. Notably, the “scenario-planning” model stands out as an extremely significant and practically applicable concept in practice

IV Questions from **the fourth group** were aimed at examining **the attitudes of respondents about whether creative thinking and innovation are important for successful integration into economic flows and starting a business**.

In general, respondents place **great importance on “soft” skills** such as **flexibility, innovativeness, and adaptability** in the business context. When it is about the flexibility, an entrepreneur highlighted that this skill is **especially crucial during the initial phase of a business**. However, another respondent cautioned that **excessive flexibility could lead to an entirely new product** when it comes to final offerings.

Entrepreneurs also state that **the key to innovation and creativity is curiosity**. In other words, they state that remaining curious until innovative solutions emerge, is essential. Managerial attitude regarding this issue was that it's crucial to **cultivate a culture that encourages sharing and accepting creative ideas and that negative consequences or punishments should not deter experimentation and novel proposals**.

In order to stimulate flexibility and innovativeness, respondents from the IT sector state that *key employees have to be given the freedom to work since “top results are made by top individuals”*.

Regarding innovativeness, one of the respondents from HR pointed that innovation is very important and is a valuable point for them in the recruitment process. They look at how creative an employee is. For example, if an employee sends the same report with the same format in 2 consecutive years, they understand that this employee has no creativity. “Creativity begins in very small things, a change in a report format, an excel database, etc. Even a change in the work environment can be a sign of creativity.”

In addition to flexibility, innovativeness and adaptability, the respondents also attached great importance to **active and continuous learning** for success in the business sphere.

In summary, the respondents state that **adaptability, creativity, and ongoing learning** contribute to overall success.

V **The fifth segment** of topics discussed in the focus group related to **proposing other “soft” skills that were not highlighted by the focus group moderators, and which are important for integration into the world of work and starting a business**. In connection with this topic, the respondents emphasized the importance of the following "soft" skills, classified upon their nature as it follows:

1. **Personal Skills:**

- **Self-motivation:** The ability to stay driven and focused without external pressure.
- **Work ethic:** Demonstrating diligence, reliability, and commitment to tasks.

- **Stress management:** Coping with pressure and maintaining emotional balance.
- **Time management:** Efficiently organizing and prioritizing tasks.
- **Ability to solve problems:** Analyzing situations and finding effective solutions.
- **Accountability:** Taking responsibility for actions and outcomes.
- **Resilience:** Bouncing back from setbacks and adapting to challenges.
- **Setting priorities:** Identifying and focusing on essential tasks.
- **Continuous learning:** Commitment to ongoing personal development.

2. Social Skills:

- **Teamwork:** Collaborating effectively with others.
- **Interpersonal relationships:** Building and maintaining positive connections.
- **Leadership:** Guiding and motivating others toward common goals.
- **Conflict resolution:** Resolving disagreements constructively.
- **Mentoring and transferring knowledge and skills:** Sharing expertise with others.
- **Active listening:** Attentively understanding and responding to others.
- **Ed**
- **Negotiation skills (part of sales skills):** Reaching mutually beneficial agreements.
- **Business ethics:** Upholding moral principles in professional conduct.

3. Methodical Skills:

- **Self-marketing:** Effectively promoting oneself or one's work.
- **Non-verbal communication:** Conveying messages through gestures, expressions, and body language.
- **Change management:** Adapting to and leading organizational changes.
- **Financial literacy (financial thinking):** Understanding financial concepts and making informed decisions.
- **"Speech communication":** Assuming this refers to effective verbal communication.

The above presented skills often complement each other, contributing to overall success in the workplace.

VI The sixth segment of questions related to examining the attitudes of respondents about the key "soft" skills that the HR department should value in candidates during the selection process, as well as which tools can be used for this purpose.

In relation to the mentioned topic, representatives from the **HR field** stated that **during the selection process**, they particularly value the following “soft” skills in candidates: **teamwork, cooperation, communication, interpersonal relationships, work ethic (responsibility, initiative, work motivation), attitude, energy (passion), flexibility**, etc., while in **leadership positions** they particularly value **leadership and mentoring ability**.

One HR respondent emphasized **professionalism, commitment, eloquence, teamwork, cultivating a winning mentality, perspective**, and **ambition** as key **soft skills**, before moving on to testing the technical hard skills. However, as one of the respondents from the **HR field** noticed, in the selection process, hard skills still prevail, and soft skills are analyzed later based on answers to certain situational questions. It was also emphasized that there are different priority skills depending on the position for which a new employee is required.

To identify these skills in candidates, a **30-minute interview** is most commonly used. During the interview, candidates are usually placed in behavioral situations to assess the extent to which individual soft skills are developed in them. In addition to the classic interview that takes place after the pre-selection of candidates, an **intelligence test**, a **team role test** (e.g., Prof. Belbin’s test), a **general knowledge test**, and a **technical knowledge test** are also recommended. After the second round of interviews, the consensus among all respondents is that at least one more round of interviews should be organized.

Not all research actors agree on whether the owner of the company should be present at the interview or not. However, in most cases, it was concluded from the research sample that owners are directly involved in the interviewing process. “Unimaginative resumes” are not considered, so it is recommended that schools focus more on training students in writing effective resumes and mastering concise pitching, which is especially valued in the selection process.

Respondents from the field of entrepreneurship indicated that **communication, proactivity, and team spirit** are extremely important skills. Additionally, **flexibility, listening ability, analytical thinking**, and **time management** were also mentioned.

VII In the last, seventh segment, questions related to the attitudes of respondents on the development of ‘soft’ skills during the educational process and during the employment phase.

Respondents highlighted that various forms of training are effective for cultivating these skills in the workplace. Additionally, they emphasized the importance of integrating diverse educational methods, including education, training, internships, and practical tasks, facilitated by experts from different fields. These methods encompass areas such as business communication, presentation skills, teamwork, workplace training, video tutorials, and checklists for technical tasks.

Furthermore, respondents recognized that **innovative curricula** can also foster soft skills. While some respondents advocated for overlapping and reinforcing these skills across both educational and work phases, others drew a distinction between the soft skills needed during education and those required for effective job performance.

During the educational process, the following soft skills were emphasized:

- **Communication skills,**
- **Active listening,**
- **Creativity,**
- **Critical thinking,**
- **Resourcefulness,**
- **Passion,**
- **The ability to perceive a real-world view of business.**

In the context of professional development at work, the focus shifted to:

- **Resilience,**
- **Teamwork,**
- **Time management,**
- **Problem-solving,**
- **Effective networking,**
- **Financial literacy,**
- **Continual learning.**

All respondents stressed the **ongoing desire to learn**, which they deemed crucial for individual growth, both during education and throughout one's career.

The respondent from the field of **entrepreneurship** aptly pointed out that no matter how well-versed we are in a particular job, **failing to adapt and improve over time can leave us obsolete due to rapid changes.**"

And finally, during the **held focus group**, a bonus question was posed: "**Is digital literacy a desirable skill and competence, and how can we encourage digital literacy among employees?**" Without any discussion, **all participants unanimously agreed** that digital literacy is a **necessary skill**. Additionally, they emphasized the importance of possessing **proficiency in the local language** and **knowledge of at least one foreign language**. Furthermore, they advocated for **promoting digital literacy prior to integration into the labor market**, as part of both **formal and informal education** for young people.

In general, the respondents agree that soft skill are important for business sphere and should be developed during educational process as well as later, during the employment phase.

REFERENCES

- Grant Agreement-Project 101120390-USE IPM (2023).
- Consortium Agreement – USE IPM project (2023).